
Ways to Provide Innovative Banking Services for Corporate Clients by Commercial Banks

To'laev Safarmurod Boymuhammad o'g'li

Is an independent researcher at Tashkent State University of Economics

Abstract: As the country's banking market has gradually developed, customers have been distributed among existing banks. To attract new customers, banks can either switch them from one bank to another or enter the market with a new type of service that meets the expectations of potential clients. The increased competition in the banking services market for corporate clients has been exacerbated by the entry of foreign banks. This requires bankers to focus on corporate clients' strategies. This approach offers several advantages for both banks and corporate clients. Creating a system for selling banking services requires theoretical research into the market for services, capital opportunities, and the main trends in national economic development, as well as potential customer needs.. Considering this, this article examines the existing problems related to the definition and solution of the problems of banks in terms of the concept, type, and classification of corporate clients when providing innovative banking services to corporate clients in developed countries. The article also discusses the author's approaches and suggestions for overcoming these problems.

Key words: commercial banks, corporate clients, banking services, market of services, new banking services, innovative banking, credit services.

Introduction. The experience of providing high-quality integrated services to corporate clients, based on the needs and demands for a specific service, is being introduced by commercial banks. This approach increases their competitiveness and helps to expand the range of services provided to clients in modern economic conditions, reduces the cost of acquiring services, improves the quality of deposit, credit and settlement services, provides corporate clients with service and professional advice from employees.

It is advisable to offer new banking services for corporate clients, to propose ideas for their creation, as well as an innovative integrated approach. In developing this approach, such aspects as focusing on the formation of an assortment of innovative banking credit services; ensuring the search for new ideas for the creation of banking credit services for corporate clients; and selecting innovative ideas for the creation of banking credit services for corporate clients are of urgent importance.

Analysis of literature on the topic. Some economists interpret the term "corporate client" in banks literally, arguing that they are only corporations, holding companies, financial-industrial groups, and other large associations.

Also, according to the definition of economists Yu. Maslanchenkov and Yu. Tronin, "...corporate clients are understood as legal entities engaged in entrepreneurial activities"[1].

According to economist I. Stoyan, "these are legal entities and individual entrepreneurs, as organizational and economic structures capable of implementing scientific, technical and technological achievements on a large scale, as well as economic organizations of small and

medium-sized businesses that counteract the oligarchic tendencies of large manufacturers and create a competitive environment, ensuring flexibility and individuality in production.”[2]

CIS economists N. Bonsevich, I. Kolbasko and L. Klimovich define a corporate client as follows: “a corporate client is a legal entity (or group) or a structural unit of a legal entity (or group thereof), the status of which and the provision of banking services to them are of significant economic interest and importance for the entire bank or its territorial divisions.” [3]

“To more clearly define the concept of "corporate client", it should be considered in conjunction with the concepts of "client" and "corporation".

A.Gryaznova muharrirligidagi ensiklopedik lug‘atda “bank mijozlari” tushunchasi quyidagicha izohlangan: “bank mijozlari - bu bank bilan qandaydir xizmatlar ko‘rsatishga oid shartnoma tuzgan yuridik va jismoniy shaxslar; naqd pulsiz hisob-kitoblarda esa bankda ochilgan hisob raqamlariga ega bo‘lgan shaxslar (shu jumladan, kredit tashkilotlari va filiallar)”[4].

According to the definition of the American economist Van Hoor: “a corporation is an impersonal enterprise created by law, capable of owning property and incurring liabilities.” [5]

Stephen Ross defines this concept as follows: “A corporation is a business entity organized as a separate legal entity, consisting of one or more individuals or legal entities.”[6] However, these general legal definitions do not reflect the economic characteristics of corporate structures.

Another economist, Yu.I. Yushko, believes that “a corporation is a large and stable financially integrated business structure that openly quotes its shares and liabilities on financial markets, is managed on the basis of uniform rules and a single methodology for all its entities, and aims to achieve maximum capitalization of its value.”[7]

At the same time, modern corporations operate in an environment with the following three characteristics:

1. The first and foremost is risk and uncertainty.
2. The second is a "return ladder" that corresponds to the stages of investment risk.
3. The third is liquidity, that is, the ability to quickly convert created products and results into the most convenient form, that is, cash flows.

Taking into account the above considerations, we consider it permissible to cite the following author's definition: the following author's definition of the concept of "corporate client of a commercial bank" is proposed: this is a legal entity or group of individuals who have a contractual relationship with the bank to provide a set of banking products and services on standard or personalized terms, which, taking into account all indicators, is sufficiently profitable for the bank.

Also, a corporate client of a commercial bank is a legal entity that uses banking services to conduct its business activities. Corporate clients can include various organizations such as enterprises, companies, government agencies, and non-profit organizations.

Research methodology. The research used scientific abstraction, grouping, comparison, retrospective and prospective, empirical analysis and other methods. The article, using the method of comparative analysis, compares the organizational and legal framework of modern methods of forming innovative banking services provided by commercial banks to corporate clients in world practice with the existing frameworks in our country, and draws appropriate conclusions.

Analysis and results. Internal advantages (and disadvantages) in the provision of banking services are usually best revealed by comparison with competitors. Therefore, banks conduct in-depth analysis of the activities of banks that are the most active market participants, offering new ways to attract and serve already active customers and potential corporate clients.

Today, banking practice is witnessing several trends in the development of banking services and products in order to retain (attract) corporate clients and generate profits. These include:

retail concept (all banking services are implemented within the framework of a program to mass attract and retain a target customer; application of elements of well-developed marketing research, structure of lines of activity: selection of a specific sector of the market and targeted promotion of existing products and services);

the concept of dumping (banks try to capture the market by offering a certain product to the client at attractive price terms);

innovative concept (using various communication methods with new customers, identifying their requirements and offering other banking products on this basis, thus creating mechanisms for retaining customers).

Figure 1. The procedure for forming corporate client strategies by commercial banks¹

In the economic literature, the concept of “customer strategy” is given various definitions. Some economists call it a “customer-oriented concept”, while others use the concept of “customer business”. According to the author, the customer strategy should be aimed at building partnerships with corporate clients, organizing the activities of a commercial bank based on a systematic study of the problems and needs of current and potential clients, as well as providing timely proposals aimed at solving their problems. This allows the client to receive additional income or other benefits.

The main principles of a corporate customer strategy should include the following:

- customer orientation;
- strategic partnership;
- maximum personalization and individualization.

The principle of customer orientation implies that the bank is focused not on its own products, but on the real needs of customers. On this basis, banks abandon the imposition of mandatory services and focus on satisfying the needs of customers to the maximum extent. This process includes clearly defining the bank's goals, formulating ways and methods to achieve them, and developing specific measures for implementation plans. This is regulated on the basis of existing and potential customer groups.

¹ Author's development

Figure 2. Stages of forming a corporate customer strategy in commercial banks²

The assessment of the bank's competitive position consists of qualitative and quantitative characteristics. Along with the general characteristics of the region, the customer base is studied by competing banks, forms and methods of customer relations, the number of points of sale in the region, groups, banking products and services, the quality and tariffs of the services provided.

For a realistic quantitative assessment of the competitiveness of a commercial bank, it is necessary to compare its current competitive position with its actual and potential competitors. For this purpose, an assessment of the competitive position according to various criteria is used: absolute market share, relative market share, market share trends, relative profitability, relative quality of

² Author's development

services, relative cost of services, emergence of new services, customer concentration, relative capital intensity.

The concept of “bank monitoring for corporate clients” can be defined as a system of continuous monitoring of the activities of corporate clients, collection and systematization of information about their financial condition, assessment of the current state and forecasting of future development. In order to address the issues of developing relations between banks and corporate clients, it is necessary to implement monitoring of corporate clients in a broad sense.

Implementing client monitoring allows a commercial bank to solve the following tasks:

1. Developing the bank's strategy to build a stable customer base, maintain relationships with priority corporate customers, develop relationships with small business customers or attract new customers, which may belong to key industry segments and corporate customer groups;
2. Conduct in-depth marketing research into customer needs and demands for new banking products and services, market capacity, customer satisfaction with banking services, etc.;
3. Formulation of the bank's overall marketing plan, product plans of business departments, sales plans of branches and their implementation.

In the scientific literature, customer grouping is sometimes equated with operational monitoring. However, in our opinion, in terms of its importance and essence, it is part of a separate corporate customer strategy for classifying existing customers.

High-quality implementation of corporate customer grouping should be carried out according to the following requirements:

- the ability to qualitatively and quantitatively assess corporate clients, the results should be presented in measurable indicators and appropriately interpreted and compared;
- the grouping results must correspond to the real situation;
- speed and simplicity in implementing grouping.

The development of the banking system, based on quantitative (growth in the number of credit institutions and banks) and qualitative (expansion of the scope of activities of banks, universalization of their activities) characteristics, implies changes in administrative and legal relations between banks and clients, especially corporate clients.

These areas will help commercial banks not only remain competitive in the market, but also increase the level of customer loyalty by providing high-quality and innovative banking services.

“... When it comes to strategic partnerships, it is worth noting that in recent years the ideology of viewing the bank as a partner has been formed. The characteristics of such relationships are: voluntariness, mutual benefit, and commercial nature.

Personalization and an individual approach are characterized by the real needs of customers. In the process of communicating with the client and analyzing the relationship, it is necessary to determine what specific and personal banking services he needs and explain to him the need and benefits of purchasing them. If earlier the bank offered a standard set of banking products, today it is advisable to develop new types of services specifically designed for specific groups of customers.

As a result of increased competition in the banking services market, the problem of timely development of a set of measures to analyze the competitive environment for the bank and maintain its competitive advantages is of particular importance. Competitive advantages include all the opportunities that distinguish the bank from other financial institutions and make it superior to its competitors. In the process of studying the various approaches presented above, it is advisable that the formation of a corporate client strategy in banks include the following main stages.

Summary. The increase in the bank's ability to provide banking services using modern technologies indicates a tendency to reorganize the processes of selling banking services. Therefore, much attention is paid to the creation of new advisory structures and mini-settlement centers for clients. The strategy of transferring a significant part of clients to self-service, while preserving the institution of personal managers for corporate clients, is becoming increasingly relevant. According to Western economists, more than 50 functions can now be performed on a self-service basis.

The current economic situation has led to a certain slowdown in the development of the retail banking market, so the main source of income for most universal banks remains servicing legal entities (corporate clients). In this regard, there is a need to search for more developed forms of relations between commercial banks and corporate clients, to formulate a corporate client strategy that reflects the bank's long-term focus on increasing competitiveness due to its dynamic adaptation to modern economic conditions and customer requirements.

Currently, our country's commercial banks are an economy of contractual relations between equal and equally responsible partners with a primary financial role. Carrying out operations on the provision of banking services, a commercial bank acts as a partner in relations with corporate clients. Innovative approaches to the provision and development of banking services to corporate clients are of interest among banks. However, the implementation of this approach is quite complicated: it is necessary to accurately calculate the time of entry into the market, support the services with a powerful advertising campaign, and in many cases such an approach provides only a short-term flow of customers, after which its effectiveness decreases.

Used references

1. Масленченков, Ю.С. Работа банка с корпоративными клиентами: Учеб. Пособие для вузов/ Ю.С. Масленченков, Ю.Н. Тронин. - Москва: Юнити-Дана, 2003. - 358 с.
2. Стоян, И.И. Развитие взаимоотношений коммерческих банков с корпоративными клиентами: автореф. дис. канд. экон. наук: 08.00.10 / И.И. Стоян; Северо-Кавказ. гос. тех. ун-т. - Ставрополь, 2006. - 24 с.
3. Bontsevich, N.V. Strategiyani rivojlantirish kommercheskogo bank: savollar nazariyasi va amaliy boshqaruv / N.V. Bontsevich, I.V. Kolbasko, L.K. Klimovich va boshqalar. - Minsk: Pravo i iqtisodiyot, 2003. - 206 s.
4. Finansova-kreditnyy entsiklopediches- kiy slovar / Pod obshchey red. prof. A.G. Griznovoy. Moskva: Moliya va statistika, 2002. - 1165 s.
5. Van Xorn, Dj. Osnovy boshqaruv fi- nansami / Per. s ingliz; Gl. qizil. Ya.V. Soko-lov. - Moskva: Finans i statistika, 2001. - 800 s.
6. Ross, S., Vesterfild, R., Djordan, B. Os- novy korporativ finansov: Per. s angl. - Moskva: Laboratoriya bazovyx znaniy, 2001. - 720 s.
7. Yushko, Yu.I. Korporativnye finansy: nazariya, metody va model boshqaruv: ucheb. metod. posobie / Yu.I. Yushko. - Minsk: "FUAinform", 2006. - 575 s.